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Does Sanskrit Provide Equivalents to New English Words?

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ABSTRACT

The phenomenon of new word formation attributes to the fact that language is an ever-evolving linguistic entity. However, English language is being hypothesized to be the most fertile language lexically as the Global Language Monitor (GLM) finds that English language reports coinage or formation of one new word almost every 98 minutes majorly because of advancement in science, technology, culture, and lifestyle. Given this high rate of new word formation in English lexicon, this reflective article aims at understanding whether do we have Sanskrit equivalents against the newly coined English words.

Keywords: Entries (words), Word formation, English, Sanskrit equivalent

1. INTRODUCTION

Language is an ever-evolving living entity, and English, being one of the world's most widely spoken languages, constantly adapts to changes in society, technology, and culture. New words are regularly introduced to describe emerging concepts, innovations, and developments in various fields. As the Sanskrit language carries with it a rich history and tradition, the idea of this study is to know whether can we coin new Sanskrit equivalents for new English words introduced in the 21st century. In this process of bridging antiquity with modernity, the prime objective is to bring Sanskrit language at par with English and making it more accessible in the modern world in terms of lexical equivalents. As for new English words, the study collected a sample of 500 English words from the official websites of Oxford English Dictionary, Cambridge Dictionary, Merriam Webster English Dictionary, Dictionary.com, and three authentic e-resources.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

A dictionary archives lexical growth of a language. More precisely, it records new words and their usage as they come into existence. The reason of lexical growth or outnumbering words in a language is not only testimony to the fact that language changes diachronically (across the time) but also because the new words keep on evolving due to advancement and new perspectives in different spheres of life such as science, technology, law, culture, management, sports, etc. The knowledge of new words in today's fast changing world is indispensable not only in having higher language proficiency in global academia but also in facilitating smoother integration into diverse cultural and social environments. According to the Global Language Monitor (GLM) there are roughly 1,019,729 words in English language and one new word is coined almost every 98 minutes globally. Viewing the outnumbering lexical entries in English lexicon, this project aims at creating an abridged dictionary of 3000 new lexical entries recorded in the past ten years and make one aware of them for daily use. To be more precise, the current project is an endeavour to firstly list up evolving new words, phrases, and expressions of English language followed by finding their Sanskrit equivalents along with their definitions and contextual usage. And this is the point of departure for this study as the researchers strongly believes that Sanskrit fraternity and Sanskrit lexicon and its users should not remain unaware of the lexical evolution happening in other languages. This statement of problem leads to set three research objectives as follows:

1.2 Research Objectives:

In line with the broad objective stated above, the study aims at achieving two specific objectives as follows:

1. *Exploring* 500 new entries added in the 21st century English lexicon.
2. Ensuring whether Sanskrit equivalents against the new English entries are at par or not.

1.1 Research Questions

Conforming to the stated research objectives above, the study has framed two research questions as follows:

1. *What are the authenticated* 500 new words of the 21st century added in the English dictionaries of higher credibility?
2. *Are* Sanskrit equivalents of the new English words at par in terms of their morphosemantic accuracy and natural acceptance?

1.3 Significance of the Study

The significance of this study is manifold. Firstly, it lets the users know about newly coined English words. Secondly, this study also provides Sanskrit equivalents which are morphologically and semantically accurate in the eyes of Sanskrit linguists and lexicographers. Thirdly, this pioneering effort makes Sanskrit language competitive in global use of modern concepts.

2. Methodology

The methodologies adopted for this study are aligned with the lexicographic framework governed by appropriate principled approaches. This study adopted a nine-layered approach to enlist close equivalents of 500 new English words as elucidated below in table-5 & table-6.